

THE IMPROVEMENT OF TEACHING OF ICT IN THE ECONOMY.**Rajabov Asliddin**

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Annotation: Knowledge and technological innovation play a crucial role in economic activities in parallel with the technological infrastructure recognized by managers, scientists, and engineers, together with the related telecommunications, information systems, environment, microelectronics machinery and computer-based transportation. As it could be easily seen, technical progress has direct effects only on production. Through process or product innovation, it is evident that to maintain a kind of feedback on education and human capital formation is the natural result of the investment inputs closely connected with the scholastic fashion. Education and technological change are major determinant of economic, cultural, political, social, demographic changes. It must be borne in mind that considering the global aspect of the economic system, one should emphasize the importance of the inclusion of information and communication technologies (ICT) in education, which naturally result in the productivity of education outputs. In parallel with the close relationship between human capital and social capital, which are closely connected with each other and at the same time trigger each other. All of them aim at the well being of economy. It related theoretical literature framework of our study would be analyzed in the light of variable such as globalization, ICT, education, human capital, social capital, and economy well being.

Key words: ICT, Economical growth, globalization, human capital, innovation

As it could be easily seen, technical progress has direct effects only on production. Through process or product innovation, it is evident that to maintain a kind of feedback on education and human capital formation is the natural result of the investment inputs closely connected with the scholastic fashion. Education and technological change are

major determinant of economic, cultural, political, social, and demographic changes. It must be born in mind that considering the global aspect of the economic system, one should emphasize the importance of the inclusion of information and communication technologies (ICT) in education, which naturally results in the productivity of education outputs, and well-being. The purpose of this study is to conduct a theoretical review on the role of education and ICT in economic growth and development. The first of the study is focused on the importance of education, globalization, and human and social capital in time. The contributions and the opportunities provided by the ICT on the process of education were examined. Subsequently, the increase in the output of education provided to the economy, and its contribution to the inventories of human and social capital were highlighted. Then, the impacts of the increase in the output of education, on the increase of human and social capital, and consequently, the enhancement created by all these factors on economic growth and development, were examined in detail on a theoretical platform.

Human capital theory amounts to the proposition that education or training can be regarded as investment with future material pay-offs, analogously to investments in physical capital (Ashton, 1996: 14, OECD, 2001: 11, OECD, 1998: 9). Education policy based on human capital concepts can address only to the first in this list of causes of economic inequality (Spring, 1998: 225). It is economic promises, education policies based on human capital theories. Human imagine being income and profit making machines. Human value is defined by an individual's worth in the labour market. The value of education becomes a function of human worth as measured by income. Social capital is simultaneously an economic, sociological concept. 'Social' and 'capital' bring together the key terms in the disciplines of sociology and political economy (Szreter, 2000: 57). A satisfactory definition therefore involves the language of both of these disciplines. One narrow meaning of social development is public welfare policies of health, communicative, social security, and housing (Pieterse, 2004: 123, Szreter, 2000: 69). The relationships between social capital and human capital are theoretically important. Some scholars have proposed that social capital helps produce human capital (Lin, 2003: 97). Well-connected parents and social ties can indeed enhance the

opportunities for individuals to obtain better education, training, lifelong learning, and skill and knowledge credentials. On the other hand, it is clear that human capital induces social capital.

The Contribution of ICT and Education to Economic Growth Technology Progress and Education. As the outcome of the emergence of global integration and the development of the knowledge-based economy, the importance of economic growth has increased within the process of economic growth. Human capital enables the production and utilization of technological knowledge. Moreover, it facilitates the harmonization of the labour power within the technological development and contributes to the process of technological progress (Gümüş, 2005: 54, McMahon, 1999: 19-33). As the result of these developments, the productivity of human is further enriched. Human capital affects the economic growth and this situation creates the emergence of positive economic externalities. These positive externalities accelerate the economic growth. Countries that accomplish a higher rate of growth give further priority to the investments in human capital. This theoretical explanation is available in the literature concerning inner growth. As the outcome of the emergence of positive economic externalities, technological development and the increase of efficiency and employment opportunities, the human capital becomes even more effective than the physical capital in economic growth (Gümüş, 2005: 55). In effect, an economic growth is accomplished, which is accompanied with the demand for qualified labour. These two economic factors interact and reinforce each other. Economic growth enhances employment opportunities, promotes higher wages for the employees and higher profits for the investors, encourages the investors and the governments to realize higher investments in human capital, and creates more abundant resources for the accomplishment of these purposes. Investments in human capital provide the necessary equipment for the creation of new employment opportunities for the labour force, and ensure a competitive edge for the global markets. All these effects facilitate and accelerate economic growth. Information and Communication Technologies Technology has evolved in the historical process through changes that formed consecutive epochs of development. When we examine the ‘Industrial Revolution’ in

history, we mark that this process has evolved in history in three revolutions (Mokyr, 2002: 78-118, Warschauer, 2003: 13). The first followed the invention of the steam engine in the eighteenth century and was characterized by the replacement of hand tools by machines, mostly in small workshops. The second followed the harnessing of electricity in the nineteenth century and was characterized by the development of large-scale factory production. The third revolution came to fruition in 1970s with the diffusion of the transistor, personal computer, and telecommunication. 'Industrial revolution' is having a large impact on the word economy.

The differences between the economies based on old industry and the new knowledge based economy are not only quantitative, but also qualitative. The world is undergoing a process of change not because the computer operators have replaced the secretaries and the typists all over the world, creating a substantial increase in efficiency, but rather because the human pursuits for survival and increase of welfare are now based on a completely different source of welfare. To the extent that agriculture based economy differs from the economy based on industry, the information technologies have created a radically different and innovative economy, which can be characterized as information based economy. Today is information century. Historically, the dramatic rate of scientific and progress has taken place alongside two other epoch-making phenomena: economic growth and social and economic globalization. Indeed, technological progress, growth, and globalization describe the three most significant aspect of the long-term evolution of the world capitalist economy. These complex phenomena are obviously interrelated, although this does not mean that the linkages can be easily specified. On the contrary, the complex relationships between technical change, growth, trade, and education are still subject to debate and controversy despite the large body of theoretical and empirical research, which does exist. Production of information and communication technology good and services has contributed quite substantially to economic growth in many developed and newly industrialized countries. ICT have altered the traditional learning environment by using new educational tools, that is to say, the concept of learning means the use of new multimedia technologies. In other words, the Internet improves

the quality of learning by facilitating access to resources and services. Thus, different strands which must be integrated into a comprehensive policy: infrastructure and equipment; high-quality educational multimedia services and content; training services and facilities for teachers and for lifelong learning; and dialogue and cooperation at all levels.

Assuming that this economic cycle operates in the global economic system, and that the economic system possesses ICT; and assuming that in this economic system, we have mainly focused on the education variable, and have considered the other variables a constant values, it can be asserted that the economic cycle operates as follows: In global economy, an education output is yielded as the outcome of the process of education, which in turn, affects the capital of the country. In our figure, it has been defined as natural and physical capital as well as 'human and social capabilities'. Human capital represents the knowledge, skills and health embodied in individuals and social capital refers to the norms and Networks facilitating co-operation either within or between groups. Political, institutional and legal arrangements interact with human and social capital to influence well-being. Additionally, human and social capitals legal also have their worn direct links with natural and produced capital. The human and social capitals, which have a direct correlation with political, institutional and legal regulations, they play a complementary function for the conventional production factors in ensuring and strengthening of economic growth and development. The enhancement of efficiency and productivity as the outcome of the existing correlation between all factors of production and the effects of positive economic externalities has a critical importance in the accomplishment of both economic growth, and socio-economic development. Conclusion A backdrop for analyzing economic and social changes is based on globalization. Education and global economy are envisioned as having an interdependent relationship. Competition in the global economy is dependent on the quality of education, whereas the goals of education are dependent on economy. Under these circumstances, education changes as the requirements of economical changes. Human capital enables the production and utilization of technological knowledge.

Moreover, it facilitates the harmonization of the labor power within the technological development and contributes to the process of technological progress. As the result of these developments, the productivity of human is further enriched. Human capital affects the economic growth and this situation creates the emergence of positive economic externalities. These positive externalities accelerate the economic growth. As the outcome of the emergence of global integration and the development of the knowledge-based economy, the importance of economic growth has increased within the process of economic growth. That kind of service aiming at the well-being of the new generations who are far away from benefiting from the advantages of the new systems of education will allow them to make use of every kind of opportunity related to not only education but also other social aspects.

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